

INVENTORY MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES IMPLEMENTATION, JOB PERFORMANCE, AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PROPERTY CUSTODIANS IN SCHOOLS DIVISION OF CALAMBA CITY

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ABSTRACT

This research assessed the level of inventory management procedures implementation, job performance, and job satisfaction among property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City. This further investigated the relationship and discovered the specific issues and concerns that contributed to inventory problems, performance issues, or employee dissatisfaction. The variables were examined using the descriptive-correlational research method. The research was conducted among property custodians and school heads of the Schools Division of Calamba City Laguna. A total of 140 surveys were collected at random using an adapted questionnaire. The data were analyzed and evaluated using the Likert Scale, t-test, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The analysis revealed that inventory management procedures were fully implemented by the property custodians of the Schools Division of Calamba City. Furthermore, there was a significant difference between the assessment of heads and property custodians' level of inventory management procedures implementation. In addition, property custodians had a very satisfactory performance in terms of quality and efficiency and outstanding performance in terms of timeliness. It has been identified that the property custodians were satisfied with their job in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Finally, the findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between the level of inventory management procedures implementation, job performance, and job satisfaction. The action plan was proposed to enhance inventory management procedures and job performance and increase job satisfaction of property custodians in

the Schools Division of Calamba City. It included storage and warehousing organization and security improvement, technology integration, procedures enhancement, continuous improvement for job performance, and motivational strategies for job satisfaction.

Keywords: *inventory management, DepEd, job satisfaction, job performance*

INTRODUCTION

The improvement of procedures is essential to keep up with an organization's changing needs. It entails locating inefficiencies, bottlenecks, and areas for improvement within the current processes and putting new procedures in place to boost productivity, cut costs, and produce better outcomes. It also helps in developing appropriate solutions to address problems.

As a business process, Inventory Management procedures are the set of steps and processes that a company uses to track, store, and manage its inventory. Effective inventory management procedures implementation requires proper planning, organization, and communication between all departments involved.

Globally, Inventory Management has been disrupted by the Covid-19 pandemic, leading to essential goods and services shortages. Two years later, most restrictions have been lifted, and the global economy is tentatively returning to how things were before. But disruptions remain. According to Curray (2022), people were still seeing the effects of the disruption in the pandemic's early months, such as continued congestion in major global ports and price rises. While people continuously recover from a pandemic, businesses should reevaluate their inventory management strategies to ensure resilience and adaptability in the face of future disruptions.

In the Philippines, several factors hinder an efficient inventory system. First off, the geography of the country makes it challenging to move goods quickly and efficiently, especially to more remote areas. As a country that is expanding economically and is fast developing, more infrastructure is needed to manage materials properly. Categorizing inventory is becoming increasingly complex due to several factors, such as supply chain disruptions, changing consumer behavior, and the proliferation of e-commerce. Now that people are in the post-pandemic era, many Filipino businesses have found innovative ways to overcome these hurdles and implement effective Inventory Management strategies. By doing so, they can streamline their operations and increase revenue by delivering superior client service.

In addition, organizations like schools and universities are responsible for keeping endless supplies and books. This includes everything from office supplies and equipment to textbooks and entire libraries of references. Most public schools in the Philippines do not have the option of purchasing the specific equipment they require. Therefore, they must be careful with their resources and make sure that there is enough inventory for the students to use in their regular classes. The most common problems in Inventory

Management in educational institutions include stock-outs, overstocking, and timeliness of inventory reports.

Efficient Inventory Management procedures could directly influence job performance. Nyamah et al. (2022) cited that when inventory flowed smoothly, employees could perform their tasks effectively and efficiently. Accurate inventory records and automated inventory management systems streamlined tasks like tracking stock levels, reordering, issuing, and disposing of items. This led to increased efficiency and improved job performance. Conversely, inefficient Inventory Management could be a significant roadblock, hindering performance and creating frustration. Manual processes like counting and updating records could be tedious and error-prone, especially when dealing with large quantities of items. Inaccurate or outdated inventory records hindered accurate demand forecasting, leading to stockouts or excess inventory. Backlogs and delays in updating inventory data could make it challenging to track real-time stock levels. Property custodians wasted precious time searching for missing items, dealt with inaccurate stock counts, and other unresolved discrepancies. These inefficiencies might lead property custodians to skip essential data collection steps, resulting in flawed information, masked discrepancies, and potential operational problems.

Furthermore, Inventory Management is also associated with job satisfaction. According to Nguyen and Vo (2023), if the procedures were done well, employees could complete tasks quickly and accurately, boosting their confidence and motivation. This fostered a sense of accomplishment and increased job satisfaction. On the other hand, poor inventory management may leave employees feeling like they are constantly playing catch-up and struggling to keep up. This lack of control may be demotivating and may lead to frustration. Disengaged employees might be less likely to follow established Inventory Management procedures, leading to non-compliance with regulations.

The reason for this study was to discover specific Inventory Management procedures that contribute to Inventory Management problems, performance issues, or employee dissatisfaction. It also aimed to create an action plan to help the organization refine its systems and implement practices that foster operational efficiency and a positive work environment.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study utilized the Implementation Theory by Palfrey as mentioned in Hayashi et al. (2020). This research examined whether it is feasible to create a system of institutions that implemented a set of normative objectives or needs when in equilibrium. Normativity was the idea that some behaviors or outcomes are standard or acceptable in society, whereas others were unwanted, or unacceptable. A norm in this context referred to a benchmark for evaluating or choosing activities or results.

Implementing the Inventory Management procedures in Philippine schools was governed by "DepEd Order No. 45 s. 2006 "Guidelines on Delivery, Inspection and Acceptance and Recording of all Properties Procured by DepEd Central Office and DBM

Procurement Service as amended by DepEd Order no. 19 s. 2007". It was issued to ensure effective and efficient delivery, inspection, and recording of all deliveries. A Property Manual Handbook was explicitly designed to guide property custodians from the complex and tedious details of asset management and procurement procedures. The following functions indicated in the manual were storage or warehousing, issuance and utilization, inventory taking, and disposal.

The Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) of the Civil Service Commission (CSC) was a tool that linked employee performance with organizational effectiveness. It ensured that the employee meet the objectives established by the organization and the organization. The guidelines stipulated the criteria and processes for performance target setting and evaluation of all employees in the department. Various performance measurement criteria were employed to guarantee an impartial, objective, and verifiable evaluation. The indicators this system used include quality, efficiency, and timeliness.

Hertzberg's two-factor theory was commonly known as Herzberg's motivation-hygiene theory. According to Baroudi et al. (2022), job satisfaction and discontent laid on two distinct continua, each with its own unique set of factors. Hertzberg explained that satisfiers or motivators were intrinsic to the work and directly related to personal growth and development. Motivators included points such as achievement, advancement, and work. On the other hand, hygiene factors or demotivators were related to the work environment and context, not the work itself. Lee et al. (2022) mentioned that hygiene factors included items like salary and benefits and working conditions. Aspects of the job might cause dissatisfaction if they are not appropriately managed. According to Manzoor et al. (2021), the two-factor theory suggested that intrinsic elements fulfilled the requirements for self-actualization and growth, which in turned leads to job satisfaction. Accordingly, Hur (2019) cited that job dissatisfaction increased when employers do not supply employees with extrinsic factors.

These theories guided this research, explored the relationship between the implementation of inventory management procedures, job performance, and job satisfaction among property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of inventory management procedures implementation among property custodians of the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their heads and property custodians in terms of:
 - 1.1 storage and warehousing,
 - 1.2 issuance and utilization,
 - 1.3 inventory taking, and
 - 1.3 disposal?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of heads and property custodians' level of inventory management procedures implementation?

3. What is the level of job performance of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of:
 - 3.1 quality,
 - 3.2 efficiency, and
 - 3.3 timeliness?
 4. What is the level of job satisfaction of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of:
 - 4.1 intrinsic factors and
 - 4.2 extrinsic factors?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the property custodians' level of inventory management procedures implementation and job performance?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the property custodians' level of inventory management procedures implementation and job satisfaction?
 7. Based on the study's findings, what action plan may be proposed?
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METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted among property custodians and school heads of Schools Division of Calamba City, Laguna. This study dwelt on the implementation of Inventory Management procedures and its effects on job performance, and job satisfaction. The study was conducted during the academic year 2023-2024. Being affiliated with the said agency, the researcher aimed to contribute scientific findings in improving the procedures of the organization.

For this research, the selection of respondents was done through a simple random sampling technique to ensure an appropriate sample. The sample size was determined using the G*power. Out of the total population of 146 DepEd property custodians and heads, a total of 140 employees (representing 96% of the population) were chosen to participate as respondents in the study.

The study's respondents were the property custodians (which were either teachers or administrative officers) and school heads of the Schools Division of Calamba City. The group of respondents included seventy (70) school heads (50%) and seventy (70) property custodians (50%). There was a total of one hundred forty (140) respondents under study.

To collect the primary data from each respondent, an adapted questionnaire was used in this research. To ensure the necessary data were accurately collected from the respondents, a three-part survey questionnaire was designed. The first part assessed the Inventory Management procedures implementation in the Schools Division of Calamba City tailored to the Inventory Management procedures manual in terms of storage and warehousing, issuance and utilization, and inventory taking and disposal. The second part determined the job performance among property custodians based on the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) of the Civil Service Commission (CSC) with determinants including quality, efficiency and timeliness while the third part assessed the

job satisfaction among property custodians based on job satisfaction standardized questionnaire in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic factors. The Inventory Management procedure's part were the changes made in the whole instrument because it was designed to match the procedures in the Schools Division of Calamba City.

The association between the degree of job performance and satisfaction of property custodians as a dependent variable and the execution of inventory management methods as an independent variable was examined using the descriptive-correlational research method. A variable that was identified was described using descriptive analysis, and its degree of relationship was ascertained using correlational analysis and statistical data.

The Likert scale was used to generate specific responses and assess the quantitative value of the dimension under consideration. The application of the Likert scale in this study was further explained by the researcher's point of view and subsequent interpretation.

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Inventory Management Procedures in Schools Division of Calamba City

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 - 4.00	4	Fully Implemented
2.50 - 3.24	3	Implemented
1.75 - 2.49	2	Partially Implemented
1.00 - 1.74	1	Not Implemented

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Job Performance among Property Custodians

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	5	Outstanding
3.40 - 4.19	4	Very Satisfactory
2.60 - 3.39	3	Satisfactory
1.80 - 2.59	2	Fairly Satisfactory
1.00 - 1.79	1	Did not Meet Expectations

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Job Satisfaction among Property Custodians

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Verbal Interpretation
3.25-4.00	4	Fully Satisfied
2.50-3.24	3	Satisfied
1.75-2.49	2	Partially Satisfied
1.00-1.74	1	Not Satisfied

To validate the instrument, the researcher first sent her adviser the researcher-adapted survey for review, approval, and additional suggested inputs. Shortly following the adviser's final evaluation, the researcher put the changes into practice. Experts that devoted their time to weighing every issue that needed to be addressed and clarified

during the study process confirmed and approved this instrument. These professionals included the statistician for the researcher, professors from LCBA, and representatives from Schools Division of Calamba City. The internal data consistency and reliability of the instrument was measured using Cronbach's Alpha. Twenty employees (20) who were not part of the respondent group participated in the instrument's pilot test.

The survey questionnaire was the primary foundation for the data collection that supported the study. The questionnaire was a primary source of information. First, the instrument's accuracy, completeness, and authenticity required the assistance of the statistician and the adviser. Second, a request for permission to collect data was made in a letter addressed to the superintendent of the Schools Division of Calamba City. Following the retrieval of the instruments, the statistician received the tabulated and totaled data from the tool. The issue statement and hypothesis of the study were applied to the analysis and interpretation of the collected data. The following statistical techniques were used for the quantitative data analysis:

1. The Mean and Likert Scale were used to describe the level of the Inventory Management procedures implementation and the level of property custodians' job satisfaction and job performance.
2. The independent t-test was used to determine the significant difference between the heads' and property custodians' assessment of the implementation of inventory management procedures in the Schools Division of Calamba City.
3. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized to measure the relationship between the level of inventory management procedures, job performance, and satisfaction among property custodians.

RESULTS

Table 1.1

Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation among Property Custodians of the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their Heads and Property Custodians in terms of Storage and Warehousing

Indicators	School Heads		Property Custodians		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Supplies, materials delivered by supplier are accompanied by Delivery Reports (DRs) and Sales Invoice (SIs).	4.00	FI	3.83	FI	3.92	FI

2. Inspection and Acceptance Report (IAR) is prepared, and the items received are properly updated to stock or property cards.	3.90	FI	3.43	FI	3.67	FI
3. Storage area is kept clean and organized at all times for fast identification of supplies.	3.83	FI	3.13	I	3.48	FI
4. Only authorized personnel are allowed to enter and stay in the stockroom to avoid theft and misplacement of supplies.	3.43	FI	3.30	FI	3.37	FI
5. The school's inventory is stored in its proper places and at its appropriate distribution points close to personnel in the area.	3.73	FI	3.29	FI	3.51	FI
General Composite Mean	3.78	FI	3.39	FI	3.59	FI

Table 1.2

Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation among Property Custodians of the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their Heads and Property Custodians in terms of Issuance and Utilization

Indicators	School Heads		Property Custodians		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. The supplies and equipment are properly charged to the requesting unit based on approved request.	3.63	FI	3.54	FI	3.59	FI
2. Supplies first added to inventory are assumed to be the first supplies removed from inventory for issuance.	3.91	FI	3.54	FI	3.73	FI
3. The product specifications, quantity and quality are checked by the inventory custodian prior to distribution.	3.80	FI	3.74	FI	3.77	FI
4. A corresponding document is issued to the requesting unit upon issuance of the supplies or equipment.	3.73	FI	3.60	FI	3.67	FI
5. Inventory record is updated after the issuance of supplies or equipment.	3.81	FI	3.20	I	3.51	FI
General Composite Mean	3.78	FI	3.53	FI	3.66	FI

Table 1.3

Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation among Property Custodians of the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their Heads and Property Custodians in terms of Inventory Taking

Indicators	School Heads		Property Custodians		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. The inventory level is regularly checked, and orders are placed on a monthly basis.	3.39	FI	3.06	I	3.23	I
2. Inventories are arranged and properly labeled with inventory tags prior to inventory taking.	3.56	FI	3.14	I	3.35	FI
3. Inventory committee is created for the conduct of physical inventory count.	3.74	FI	3.10	I	3.42	FI
4. Inventory taking of supplies is done every 6 months while the inventory of equipment is undertaken for at least once a year.	3.61	FI	3.47	FI	3.54	FI
General Composite Mean	3.58	FI	3.19	I	3.39	FI

Table 1.4

Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation among Property Custodians of the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their Heads and Property Custodians in terms of Disposal

Indicators	School Heads		Property Custodians		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. The accountable person returns the unserviceable items to the property custodian.	3.83	FI	3.50	FI	3.67	FI
2. The property custodian files an application for disposal together with appropriate documents to the Auditor.	3.39	FI	3.13	I	3.26	FI
3. The auditor inspects the items to determine their value and give recommendations to the head of office.	3.26	FI	2.79	I	3.03	I
4. The property custodian forwards the documents to the disposal committee.	3.63	FI	3.19	I	3.41	FI
5. The disposal committee recommends the most appropriate mode of disposal to the head of office.	3.47	FI	3.00	I	3.24	I
General Composite Mean	3.51	FI	3.12	I	3.32	FI

Table 2

Test of Significant Difference between the Assessment of Heads and Property Custodians' Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation

Variables	t-test	P value	Remarks	Decision
storage and warehousing	5.548	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
issuance and utilization	4.246	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
inventory taking	5.105	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
disposal	4.645	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Table 3.1

Level of Job Performance of Property Custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Quality

Indicators	School Heads	
	X	VI
1. Reflect work thorough, and current knowledge/skill of job impact on agency activities/related resources.	4.03	VS
2. Use opportunities to expand knowledge/skills, sharing information with staff.	4.09	VS
3. Consistently exceed expectations of work quality, quantity, customer service and timeliness standards.	3.91	VS
4. Consistently and significantly exceeded job expectations and standards and demonstrates a high degree of initiative, customer service, and quality of work.	3.93	VS
5. Consistently promote and maintain a harmonious/productive work environment.	4.20	O
6. Suggest innovations to improve operations or streamline procedures.	3.94	VS
7. Define and analyze complex problems.	3.97	VS
8. Serve as a role model about adherence to work policies and safety standards.	3.97	VS
General Assessment	4.01	VS

Table 3.2

Level of Job Performance of Property Custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Efficiency

Indicators	School Heads	
	X	VI
1. Regularly exceeded expectations.	3.93	VS
2. Implement innovative policies, and use resources, and technology to maximize productivity and service.	3.87	VS
3. Commit to and promote excellence, led by example, energize performance and teamwork.	4.00	VS
4. Use and encourage creative decisions and solutions.	3.92	VS
5. Act as a positive change agent.	3.94	VS
6. Play as a role model and be recognized as respectable and trusted.	4.13	VS
7. Articulately and persuasively present and solicit complex or sensitive data.	4.00	VS
8. Prevent/resolve unit/team problems.	4.00	VS
General Assessment	3.97	VS

Table 3.3

Level of Job Performance of Property Custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Timeliness

Indicators	School Heads	
	X	VI
1. Communicate in a clear, effective, timely, concise and organized manner.	4.19	VS
2. Develop or implement solutions with low supervision.	4.16	VS
3. Reflect on work on maximum, innovative use of time and resources to consistently surpass expectations and improve operations.	4.09	VS
4. Answer queries for delivery of service.	4.27	O
5. Response to client needs.	4.40	O
6. Prepare monthly reports on time.	4.23	O
General Assessment	4.22	O

Table 4.1

Level of Job Satisfaction of Property Custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Intrinsic Factor

Indicators	Property Custodians	
	X	VI
1. Being able to keep busy all the time.	3.20	S
2. The chance to work alone on the job.	3.29	FS
3. The chance to do different things from time to time.	3.01	S
4. Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience.	3.26	FS
5. The chance to do things for other people.	3.31	FS
6. The chance to tell people what to do.	3.17	S
7. The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.	3.36	FS
8. The chances for advancement on this job.	3.11	S
9. The freedom to use my own judgment.	3.23	S
10. The chance to try my own methods of doing the job.	3.23	S
11. The praise I get for doing a good job.	2.96	S
12. The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	3.27	FS
General Assessment	3.20	S

Table 4.2

Level of Job Satisfaction of Property Custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Extrinsic Factors

Indicators	Property Custodians	
	X	VI
1. The chance to be "somebody" in the community.	3.13	S
2. The way my boss handles his/her workers.	3.20	S
3. The competence of my supervisor in making decisions.	3.19	S
4. The way my job provides for steady employment.	3.41	FS
5. The way company policies are put into practice.	3.04	S
6. My pay and the amount of work I do.	2.56	S
7. The working conditions.	2.76	S
8. The way my co-workers get along with each other.	3.09	S
General Assessment	3.05	S

Table 5

Test of Significant Relationship between the Property Custodians' Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation and Job Performance

Inventory Management	Job Performance	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Storage and warehousing	Quality	.371**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Efficiency	.344**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Timeliness	.298**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Issuance and utilization	Quality	.413**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Efficiency	.406**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Timeliness	.411**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Inventory taking	Quality	.436**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Efficiency	.418**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Timeliness	.328**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Disposal	Quality	.398**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Efficiency	.375**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Timeliness	.244**	.004	Significant	Reject Ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6

Test of Significant Relationship between the Property Custodians' Level of Inventory Management Procedures Implementation and Job Satisfaction

Inventory Management	Job Satisfaction	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Storage and warehousing	Intrinsic	.242**	.004	Significant	Reject Ho
	Extrinsic	.206*	.015	Significant	Reject Ho
Issuance and utilization	Intrinsic	.186*	.028	Significant	Reject Ho
	Extrinsic	.168*	.047	Significant	Reject Ho
Inventory taking	Intrinsic	.188*	.026	Significant	Reject Ho
	Extrinsic	.248**	.003	Significant	Reject Ho
Disposal	Intrinsic	.152	.073	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Extrinsic	.201*	.017	Significant	Reject Ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 7

The Proposed Action Plan

General Objective: To enhance the inventory management procedures and job performance and increase job Satisfaction of property custodians in Schools Division of Calamba City

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	FREQUENCY	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Storage and Warehousing Organization and Security Improvement	To address organization and security concerns of inventory management in terms of storage and warehousing	Regular cleaning and organization of the storage area – use the 5 S method (Sort, Set in order, Shine, Standardize and Sustain) Evaluate the capacity of the space and propose expansion if needed Implement a logical storage and warehouse layout that includes classifying objects	Whole year round and semi-annually	Property Custodians and Heads	90% of the storage area is clean, organized and there is faster identification of supplies 100% of the personnel entering the storage are those authorized only

according to how frequently they are used to for fast identification of supplies.

Secure storage entry points.

Mark restricted areas with signage and warnings.

Educate employees about restricted areas and proper access procedures.

(continuation)

Issuance and Utilization Technology Integration

To streamline the procedures in updating inventory records

Implementing Inventory Management Systems Technologies like barcode and Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) scanning to automate tracking, reduce errors

Whole year round

ICT Personnel, Property Custodians and Heads

90% of the transactions are fully automated

		and real-time visibility.			
		Investing in Inventory Management Software to generate reports and optimize ordering decisions			
Inventory Taking Efficiency	To facilitate procedures in inventory taking	Creation of school-based inventory committee to assist in the regular inventory taking procedures	Semi-annually	Property Custodians and Heads	90% of the inventory is regularly checked
Disposal Procedures Enhancement	To achieve full implementation of disposal procedures	Creation of school-based disposal committee and conduct trainings reiterating the value of adhering to the proper disposal procedures	Semi-annually	Property Custodians, Disposal Committee, Auditor and Heads	90% of the condemned properties are disposed properly
Continuous Improvement for Job Performance	To apply total quality management to exceed expectations of work standards	Set clear organizational aims and objectives for work quality, efficiency and timeliness	Whole year round	Property Custodians and Heads	90% Implementation of TQM and SPMS Programs

To create chances for the adoption of creative policies and the efficient use of resources and technology in order to boost productivity.

Provide relevant training, mentoring and coaching programs to encourage continuous learning and provide support for improvement

Provide timely and constructive feedback that focuses on strengths and areas for improvement and implement performance-based incentives to motivate exceeding expectations Foster a culture of empowerment where property custodians would feel encouraged to use their skills and knowledge to find

		innovative solutions			
		Identify specific areas for improvement in productivity and operations and choose technologies that address those needs directly			
Motivational Strategies for Job Satisfaction	To improve job satisfaction about the recognition given to employees	Conduct semi – annual performance review and recognition on job performance of property custodians	Semi-annually	Property custodians and Heads	80% of employees will be fully satisfied about recognition and awards
	To improve job satisfaction about the pay and amount of work employees do	Increase benefits and incentives for the productivity of the employees			
		Employ additional workforce to delegate excessive tasks to other personnel			

DISCUSSION

Storage and Warehousing was Fully Implemented (3.59) as to the level of implementation of the Inventory Management procedures among the property custodians of the Schools' Division of Calamba City as assessed by their heads and property custodians. The indicator "Supplies and other materials delivered by suppliers are accompanied by Delivery Reports (DRs) and Sales Invoice (SIs) obtained the highest mean score of 3.92 verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. On the other hand, the indicator "Only authorized personnel are allowed to enter and stay in the stockroom to avoid theft and misplacement of supplies" received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.37 verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented.

This means that there is high adherence to Inventory Management procedures across the indicators. This suggests that the schools in Calamba City have established and maintained standard systems for managing their inventory in terms of storage and warehousing which is crucial for the smooth operation of educational institutions. The structured and formalized process of receiving supplies ensures proper documentation and verification of delivered items. The high adherence to this procedure reflects a solid commitment to transparency and accuracy in handling school supplies and materials. However, it can be observed that the lowest mean score is associated with the indicator "Only authorized personnel are allowed to enter and stay in the stockroom to avoid theft and misplacement of supplies. This might indicate minor challenges in enforcing restricted access to storage areas. Controlling access to stockrooms is a critical aspect of Inventory Management, as it minimizes the risks of theft, misplacement, or mishandling of supplies. The relatively lower score in this area could suggest a need for more stringent enforcement of access policies or perhaps a need for increased awareness and training for staff regarding the importance of restricted access to these areas. Moreover, the emphasis on keeping storage areas clean and organized got a low score from the property custodians' assessment. This further suggests difficulties in organizing the storage or warehousing area. An organized storage area is an essential aspect of Inventory Management as it affects the efficiency of the organization's day-to-day operations.

Issuance and Utilization was Fully Implemented (3.66) as to the level of Inventory Management procedures implementation among property custodians of the Schools' Division of Calamba City as assessed by their heads and property custodians. The indicator "The product specifications, quantity and quality are checked by the inventory custodian prior to distribution" obtained the highest mean score of 3.73 verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. On the other hand, the indicator "Inventory record is updated after the issuance of supplies or equipment" received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.51 verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented.

The data reveal a consistently high level of implementation across various indicators. It suggests a strong and organized method for controlling the distribution and use of resources and equipment. Specifically, the method of charging supplies and equipment to the unit making the request, in accordance with authorized demands,

illustrates a methodical and responsible approach to resource allocation. This suggests that the schools have established clear protocols to ensure that resources are distributed according to planned and approved needs, thereby enhancing efficiency and reducing wastage. Applying the First-In-First-Out (FIFO) method demonstrates a strategic approach to managing inventory turnover. This method, which assumes that the first supplies added to inventory are the first to be removed is crucial for minimizing the risk of obsolescence, especially in educational settings where certain supplies may have limited shelf life. The high score in this area suggests that the schools are effectively managing their inventory to ensure that older stock is used first, thereby maintaining the quality and relevance of the supplies. The practice of checking product specifications, quantity, and quality by the inventory custodian before distribution underscores the commitment to maintaining high standards in utilizing supplies. This step is vital for ensuring that the items distributed meet the required standards and are fit for their intended use. Additionally, issuing corresponding documents to the requesting unit upon the distribution of supplies or equipment highlights a transparent and traceable process essential for accountability and record-keeping.

However, a notable area for improvement is observed in the updating of inventory records after the issuance of supplies or equipment; this lower score suggests challenges in consistently updating inventory records post-issuance. It can be observed that property custodians need help in updating the inventory records promptly. However, establishing an Inventory Management system may assist the custodians in keeping the records up to date. Timely and accurate record-keeping is crucial for maintaining an up-to-date understanding of inventory levels and planning future procurement and utilization. Relative to this, Aladi (2019) conducted a study titled "Automating School Fees Transactions in Nigerian Universities and Tertiary Institutions: A Systems Engineering and System Management Approach." While focusing on financial transactions, this research highlighted the importance of system management and automation in educational institutions. The principles discussed in automating transactions, including centralized data, automated reports, and inventory controls, were directly applicable to efficient inventory issuance and utilization management. The study underscored the benefits of integrating technology to streamline processes and enhance accountability.

Inventory Taking was Fully Implemented (3.39) as to the level of inventory taking aspect of Inventory Management procedures in the Schools Division of Calamba City assessed by the school heads, and property custodians. The indicator "Inventory taking of supplies is done every 6 months while the inventory of equipment is undertaken for at least once a year" obtained the highest mean score of 3.54 verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. Meanwhile, the indicator "The process of regularly checking inventory levels and placing orders on a monthly basis" scored a composite mean of 3.23 verbally interpreted as Implemented.

This shows that there is a systematic approach to taking inventory. Accounting for supplies and equipment every six months and at least once a year indicates a proactive approach to Inventory Management. This ensures the schools have a regular and updated understanding of their asset and supply levels. Scheduled inventory taking is critical for effective resource management, allowing for timely identification of

discrepancies, loss of critical equipment, or alerts for replenishment. Determining the count and condition of the supplies and equipment assists the management in determining which items the schools need and which should be given priority. This clearly supports the management in making critical decisions.

Nevertheless, some areas indicate a need for improvement in making this process more consistent and efficient. There is a need for consistently and regularly checking inventory levels. It shows that property custodians need help in regularly checking inventory levels because manually checking the inventory is labor-intensive. Property custodians must manually count all the inventory on hand to update the records regularly. This task is time-consuming and overwhelming for property custodians as they have many other administrative tasks besides their property functions. Regular inventory checks are crucial in educational settings to ensure the smooth functioning of day-to-day educational activities. It is vital for maintaining the balance between availability and optimal use of resources in educational institutions, ensuring that the needs of students and staff are met efficiently. In support of this, Wynn and Kuhn (2021) cited that manual inventory taking was incredibly time-consuming. This was especially true for businesses with large or complex types of items in storage. Employees might need to physically count every item, often multiple times a year, which could take hours, days, or even weeks, depending on the size and complexity of the inventory. Manually managing an inventory might require additional employees, resulting in additional costs.

Disposal was Fully Implemented (3.32) as to the level of disposal procedures in Inventory Management within the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their heads and property custodians. The indicator “The accountable person returns the unserviceable items to the property custodian” obtained the highest mean score of 3.67 verbally interpreted as Fully Implemented. On the other hand, the indicator “The auditor inspects the items to determine their value and give recommendations to the head of office” received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.03 verbally interpreted as Implemented.

This reveals that disposal procedures are followed, though there are still signs of improvement in other areas. The procedure for returning unserviceable items to the property custodian reflects a well-structured system where accountability is clearly defined. This high score suggests a strong understanding and implementation of handling unserviceable items, ensuring they are appropriately managed and not left to cause clutter or inefficiency within the school's inventory system.

However, it can also be observed that some procedures need to be more strictly followed, such as the auditor's role to inspect items and provide recommendations. This step is crucial as it determines the value of items and guides the decision-making process for their disposal. The lower score could be due to cost, time, and other reasons. Most of the items disposed of were books, furniture, and other items that have physically deteriorated due to natural means such as pests, floods, and other similar causes. Many of these properties have become low-valued or have no commercial value. Due to inadequate space, these items should be disposed as soon as possible. If the value of the items is too low, it would be more practical to have alternative modes of responsible

disposal. This may be mitigated through items such as internal controls and documented procedures, rather than inviting the division auditors in the field to witness the actual procedures of the disposal. However, an audit can be a valuable safeguard for high-value disposals, complex properties, or situations with a high risk of error or fraud.

Likewise, the process of forwarding documents to the disposal committee and the committee's recommendation on the mode of disposal indicate a well-established but potentially weak point in the process. This might hint at challenges in establishing a disposal committee or understanding the procedural requirements. These steps are vital for ensuring that the disposal of items is conducted in an efficient, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective manner. It also ensures transparency and compliance with regulatory requirements, making it a critical aspect of the disposal process. Moreover, Rachman (2023) stated that optimal asset disposal was required to reduce the burden on the organization and improve efficiency. However, disposal was frequently complicated and time-consuming. Delayed disposal caused storage problems and economic devaluation. These practices might result in safety risks, inefficient resource allocation, and missed deadlines and delays. By recognizing these challenges, organizations might transform their asset disposal process from chaotic into streamlined and responsible practices.

There was a significant difference between the assessment of heads and property custodians' level of inventory management procedures implementation. The probability values were all .000, which were less than the significance level at .05. The null hypothesis was rejected due to these values.

This significant perception disparity could be attributed to various factors inherent in the roles and responsibilities of both parties. School heads, who are typically more removed from the day-to-day operations of Inventory Management, might have a different perspective on the effectiveness and implementation of these procedures compared to property custodians, who are directly immersed in these processes. The custodians' hands-on experience might give them a more critical and detailed view of the implementation challenges and practicalities. In contrast, school heads might base their assessments on policy compliance and overall outcomes.

The findings underscore the importance of fostering effective communication and understanding between different stakeholders in the Inventory Management process. The significant differences in perception highlighted by this analysis suggest a potential gap in shared understanding or expectations regarding Inventory Management practices. It highlights an opportunity for enhancing inventory management practices through improved communication, training, and collaboration.

Quality was Very Satisfactory (4.01) as to the level of job performance of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Quality as assessed by their school heads. The indicator "consistently promote and maintain a harmonious/productive work environment" had the highest mean score of 4.20 verbally interpreted as Outstanding while the indicator "consistently exceed expectations of work

quality, quantity, customer service and timeliness standards” had the lowest mean of 3.91 verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

The findings indicate a strong and consistent performance by property custodians in aspects related to the quality of their work. It suggests they are well-versed in their roles and contribute significantly to the agency's functioning. Their willingness to use opportunities to expand knowledge and share information points to a culture of continuous learning and collaboration. In addition, they reflect a proactive and dedicated approach to job responsibilities. The property custodians exhibit initiative, beyond the standard of client service, and high-quality work, meeting, and often exceeding job requirements. They also exhibit the ability to innovate and tackle complex issues, which is crucial in the dynamic environment of school administration. Maintaining a high standard of work can assist employees in gaining new experiences, information, and abilities that will further their professional and personal development. It may result in opportunities for career progress and higher levels of motivation, confidence, and job satisfaction.

Efficiency was Very Satisfactory (3.97) as to the level of job performance of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City as assessed by their school heads. The indicator “play as a role model and be recognized as respectable and trusted” had the highest mean score of 4.14 verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory while the indicator “implement innovative policies, and use resources, and technology to maximize productivity and service” had the lowest mean of 3.87 verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

This high scores across all indicators suggests that property custodians are practical and efficient. They have a proactive approach to job responsibilities. The custodians are seen as leaders who commit to excellence, maintain performance, and promote teamwork. The findings also show their influential position in the organization. Their ability to articulate and persuade and to prevent and resolve problems within their units demonstrates their competence in communication and conflict resolution. In addition, property custodians can be regarded as highly competent, efficient, and effective in their roles. A strong commitment to quality, continuous improvement, and teamwork define their performance. These attributes are essential in ensuring the smooth operation and administration of school resources, contributing significantly to the overall effectiveness of the educational institution.

Timeliness was Outstanding (4.22) as to the level of job performance of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City in terms of Timeliness as assessed by their school heads. The indicator “response to client needs” had the highest mean score of 4.41 verbally interpreted as Outstanding while the indicator “reflect on work on maximum, innovative use of time and resources to consistently surpass expectations and improve operations.” had the lowest mean of 4.09 verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

The findings indicate an exceptional level of performance in this area. The property custodians are proficient in their communication skills and ensure that their interactions are timely and efficient, which is crucial in the fast-paced environment of school

administration. The ability to develop or implement solutions with minimal supervision highlights the custodians' level of independence and initiative. This independence is vital in a role often requiring quick decision-making and problem-solving without direct oversight. They also can efficiently manage their workload and resources, surpassing expectations and continuously seeking ways to improve operations. The high scores in responding to client needs and preparing monthly reports on time demonstrate a solid commitment to service delivery and adherence to deadlines. These aspects are critical in maintaining the smooth operation of the schools and ensuring that all stakeholders meet their needs promptly and effectively.

Intrinsic Factors was Satisfied (3.20) as to the level of job satisfaction of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City. The indicator "The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities" had the highest mean score of 3.36 verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied while the indicator "The praise I get for doing a good job" had the lowest mean of 2.96 verbally interpreted as Satisfied.

The findings show a positive level of intrinsic job satisfaction. The indicators reveal that the custodians feel that they have the opportunity to use their abilities. By using their capacities, they can use it to do things for other people. This results in having a feeling of accomplishment from doing the job. This engagement is crucial for job satisfaction as it ensures employees feel their work is meaningful and contributes significantly to the organization. This sense of achievement and the ability to utilize one's skills effectively are critical drivers of intrinsic job satisfaction.

The other indicators reveal that they need more recognition to fulfill their job. They are also satisfied with doing many different things from time to time. They also want to execute their tasks independently by using their judgment or trying their methods in doing their job. It suggests a degree of autonomy and variety in their roles, which can be highly motivating and satisfying. They also feel that they need more chances for advancement. Enhancement in these areas may further increase job satisfaction.

Extrinsic Factors was Satisfied (3.05) as to the level of job satisfaction of property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City. The indicator "the way my job provides for steady employment." had the highest mean score of 3.41 verbally interpreted as Fully Satisfied while the indicator "my pay and the amount of work I do." had the lowest mean of 2.56 verbally interpreted as Satisfied.

The findings indicate that property custodians are fully satisfied with the job stability that the employer can provide. It assures them that they can continue their work in the foreseeable future. However, some indicators of extrinsic factors reveal that they are not fully satisfied with the pay for their work and the working conditions. Also, they have more expectations when it comes to the manifestation of the policies and their collaboration with their superiors and co-workers. These factors ensure overall job satisfaction and can impact morale and productivity.

There was significant relationship between the property custodians' level of Inventory Management procedures implementation and job performance. The probability

values were all 0.000, thus less than the significance level of .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. There was a substantial relationship between the property custodians' level of inventory management procedures implementation and job performance. The degree of correlations between Inventory Management procedures and job performance were moderate, (value between ± 0.300 and ± 0.490) which suggested a noticeable, but not overwhelmingly strong, connection between how effectively inventory is managed and the overall performance of employees. It suggests that there is some connection between the two variables in question, but there is also a lot of randomness affecting one or both variables, or there are other variables influencing the two variables in question the relationship between the two factors isn't strong, other factors like employee training, company culture, and workload could play a significant role. While showing a significant correlation with job performance, the disposal process has a slightly lower significant relationship on timeliness. While disposal practices are essential, their influence on the timeliness aspect of job performance is less pronounced compared to other inventory management areas.

The results suggest that effective Inventory Management positively influences job performance. For instance, the correlation between storage and warehousing and aspects of job performance like quality, efficiency, and timeliness indicates that well-organized and efficiently managed storage systems contribute to overall job effectiveness. It could be attributed to efficient storage and warehousing practices streamlining processes, reducing errors, and saving time, thereby enhancing the overall quality and efficiency of work. Similarly, the correlation between issuance and utilization and job performance metrics underscores the importance of proper management in the distribution and utilization of resources. Effective issuance and utilization practices ensure that resources are optimally allocated and used, directly influencing job performance, quality, and efficiency. Inventory taking with similar moderate degree of correlation also significantly affects job performance, particularly in quality and efficiency. Regular and accurate inventory checks contribute to a better understanding of resource availability and needs, influencing the quality and efficiency of job execution.

There was significant relationship between the property custodians' level of Inventory Management procedures implementation and job satisfaction. The probability values of .004, .015, .028, .047, .026, .003, and .017 were all less than the significance level at .05, thus rejecting the null. There was a substantial relationship between the property custodians' level of Inventory Management procedures implementation and job satisfaction. However, there was no significant relationship between disposal and intrinsic. The probability of .073 was greater than the significance level at .05. Thus, accept the null hypothesis. The degree of correlation between Inventory Management procedures and intrinsic and extrinsic factors showed a small correlation (below $\pm .290$) between these variables.

This means that changes in Inventory Management practices were unlikely to have a consistent influence on employee satisfaction. Beyond Inventory Management, a wide range of elements influence the complicated and multifaceted concept of job satisfaction. Salary, workload, leadership, corporate culture, and personal factors also play significant

roles. As a result, even if Inventory Management is efficient, its impact on overall satisfaction might be masked by the influence of other variables.

The results suggest that effective Inventory Management positively influences job satisfaction. The correlation between storage and warehousing and intrinsic job satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction implies that well-managed storage systems not only satisfy the internal motivations of employees but also positively impact external satisfaction factors like work environment and working conditions. In the context of issuance and utilization, the correlations with intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction suggest that efficient management in these areas contributes to a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction with external job aspects. Inventory taking shows a similar pattern, significantly related to extrinsic and intrinsic job satisfaction. It indicates that regular and accurate inventory checks contribute to a sense of achievement and satisfaction derived from the company policies and environment. However, in the case of disposal, there is a significant relationship with extrinsic job satisfaction, but the correlation with intrinsic satisfaction is not significant. While disposal practices are associated with external factors of job satisfaction, they do not significantly influence the internal satisfaction derived from the job.s

Conclusions

After the presentation of the study's summary of findings, the following conclusions were made:

1. That the schools in the Division of Calamba City have established and maintained standard systems for managing inventory which is crucial for the smooth operations of educational institutions. They have a systematic approach and create clear protocols to ensure inventory is managed correctly. However, some of the indicators show some challenges, especially in the storage organization and security, manual procedures, number of personnel, and disposal requirements, which implies room for improvement in making the process more consistent and efficient.
2. That perceptions of school heads and property custodians in the Schools Division of Calamba City are not the same as to Inventory Management procedures. This suggests that school heads might not fully understand the practical challenges faced by property custodians, leading to unrealistic expectations or ineffective solutions. Addressing these differences is crucial for improving inventory management's overall efficiency and effectiveness in the Schools Division of Calamba City.
3. That there is a strong and consistent performance by property custodians in aspects related to their work's quality, efficiency, and timeliness. This shows that they are highly competent, efficient, and effective. A solid commitment to quality, continuous improvement, innovation, and teamwork marks their performance. These attributes are

essential in ensuring the smooth operation and administration of school resources, contributing significantly to the overall effectiveness of the educational institution.

4. That property custodians feel empowered to work independently and have confidence in their skill, leading to higher productivity. They are also fully satisfied with the stability of employment. It gives them the feeling of security in their jobs. However, property custodians need to be fully satisfied with some indicators, such as recognition, chances for advancement, and freedom to use their judgment and methods. This also includes their perception of leadership and management within schools, the company policies in practice, camaraderie among their co-workers, working conditions, and the pay and the amount of work they do, which suggest areas for improvement. This points to property custodians feeling partially fulfilled but not fully satisfied can create internal conflict, leading to stress, anxiety, and even burnout. If employees feel their needs aren't fully met, they may be more likely to seek new opportunities elsewhere. Further, increased turnover and lower productivity could lead to higher costs for the organization.

5. That well-organized and efficiently managed inventory systems contribute to overall job effectiveness. Efficient Inventory Management practices streamlining processes, reducing errors, and saving time, thereby enhancing the overall quality and efficiency of work. The moderate degree of correlation implies that other factors like employee training, company culture, and workload could play a significant role.

6. That well-managed Inventory Management systems not only satisfy the internal motivations of employees but also positively associate with external satisfaction factors like work environment and working conditions. However, in the case of disposal, there was a significant relationship with extrinsic job satisfaction, but the correlation with intrinsic satisfaction is not significant. While disposal practices are associated with external factors of job satisfaction, they do not significantly influence the internal satisfaction derived from the job. The small degree of correlation between these variables implies that beyond inventory management, a wide range of elements such as salary, workload, leadership, corporate culture, and personal factors influence the complicated and multifaceted concept of job satisfaction. Thus, it suggests that even if inventory management is efficient, its impact on overall satisfaction might be masked by the influence of other variables.

7. That the proposed action plan is necessary in response to the study, incorporating new tactics regularly to fortify the implementation of inventory management procedures in Schools Division of Calamba City and to concurrently improve the job performance and satisfaction of property custodians.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, suggestions, and recommendations were listed below:

1. The Inventory Management procedures set by the among property custodians in Schools Division of Calamba City may be maintained and undergo enhancement. The

heads may initiate programs and systems that will address issues in storage and warehousing, issuance and utilization, inventory taking and disposal. They may implement strategies that will optimize efficiency, maintain cleanliness and organization and secure restricted storage areas. They may also implement Inventory Management systems to streamline the procedures in updating inventory records, reducing errors and improving visibility. Heads may create school-based inventory and disposal committee to facilitate concerns in inventory taking and disposal. Most schools, especially non-implementing units, have only one property custodian assigned in the whole Inventory Management process. Some of them are teachers, while others are administrative officers doing other administrative tasks like finance, HR functions and others. It would help reduce the property custodian's huge workload. Lastly, the management may opt for alternative modes of responsible disposal especially low value items to expedite the disposal procedure.

2. Addressing the perception differences between property custodians and heads, the Schools Division of Calamba City may involve more collaborative planning and review sessions, targeted training programs to align understanding and practices. Regular feedback mechanisms to ensure that both heads and custodians are aligned regarding Inventory Management standards and expectations may be performed.

3. Sustaining and enhancing the very satisfactory rating on the performance of property custodians, Schools Division of Calamba City may set clear goals for work quality, efficiency, and timeliness. This clarity allows employees to focus their efforts, track progress and understand both minimum requirements and "what exceeding expectations" looks like in concrete terms. The management may also provide relevant training, support and performance-based incentives to motivate exceeding expectations of work quality, efficiency and timeliness. They may also help property custodians implement innovative policies and use resources and technology to maximize productivity and improve operations.

4. Improving the satisfactory rating of job satisfaction among property custodians, the management may give recognition and awards for the job performance of property custodians. The management may also discuss additional salaries and benefits to better compensate property custodians for the amount of work they do. In addition, providing them with safe and healthy working conditions, positive and supportive work environments, and a well-managed workload may improve their physical and mental health, foster employee engagement and satisfaction, boost motivation, and lead to higher productivity. Finally, the management may add personnel to assist property custodians in their functions. This may also help increase their responsiveness to accommodate requests, especially property custodians assigned with a high number of personnel.

5. Strengthening the significant relationship between the implementation of Inventory Management procedures and job performance, the management of the Schools Division of Calamba City may streamline the Inventory Management procedures by having clear and concise procedures. This may also be done by having standardized practices and leveraging technology to automate routine tasks such as inventory tracking, reorder

points and data analysis. This frees up employee time for higher-value activities and improves accuracy. In addition, the management may foster open communication channels between management and property custodians regarding inventory procedures, updates, and challenges. Regular feedback from the property custodians on their experience with inventory management can be used to identify areas for improvement and ensure the procedures are user-friendly and effective.

6. Boosting the significant relationship between the implementation of Inventory Management procedures and job satisfaction, the management of the Schools Division of Calamba City may make the current Inventory Management procedures more user friendly and efficient. This may be done by simplifying complex procedures, minimizing manual efforts and provide user-friendly tools for Inventory Management tasks. Also, they may offer regular training and support to ensure that property custodians have adequate training on all procedures and access to ongoing support when needed. Furthermore, management may empower and involve property custodians by allowing them to have inputs on inventory procedures and decision making, promoting teamwork and collaboration, providing opportunities for growth and development, and recognizing and rewarding accomplishments. In addition, to strengthen the relationship of disposal practices and intrinsic factors, raising awareness about the environmental impact of different disposal practices helps property custodians to make informed choices based on their intrinsic values. Moreover, it may also help if there are simplified and accessible systems of disposal to make it easier to adopt to sustainable practices.

7. The Schools Division of Calamba City may implement the proposed action plan or program focusing on streamlined inventory management processes, efficient and satisfied employees.

8. More literature on the subject and more research on Inventory Management procedures implementation, job performance, and job satisfaction may be done. There is a growing need for more empirical research to provide concrete evidence and practical insights. It is also advised that future studies take a qualitative rather than a quantitative approach to better comprehend the experiences of the property custodians. To bridge the gap between inventory management practices, job performance, and job satisfaction among property custodians at educational institutions, this may offer a deeper viewpoint. In addition, additional topics may be explored, focusing on emerging trends such as investigating the role of automation and robotics in inventory management, exploring the impact of sustainable inventory practices and study about the influence of remote work and hybrid models in inventory management. These studies may help analyze how these topics influence employee tasks, skills, and satisfaction within the context of inventory management.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical issues were an important aspect of research. Prior to the trial, the researcher sought informed consent from the respondents. The surveys contained no derogatory, discriminatory, or otherwise inappropriate wording that could have offended any of the group members. Questionnaires were intended to collect information that is

specifically relevant to the study objectives; no private or personal information is collected through them. The LCBA Thesis Writing Manual was followed, and no disclosure of respondents' personal identities was made or disclosed to any individual in any manner in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

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